

Customizing Your Diet with Ayurvedic Prakriti Prediction using ANN

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Abstract—In today's fast-paced world, many individuals lead modern lifestyles with little time for self-care, leading to serious health issues. The role of food intake in human health is of great significance, and Ayurveda provides a unique approach that blends modern lifestyle and health-oriented habits. At the heart of Ayurveda's approach is the concept of Prakriti, which determines an individual's diet (ahara), lifestyle (vihara), behavior (achara), and remedial measures (parihara) to achieve optimal health. Despite this, many individuals blindly follow media sources recommendations for diet and nutrition, which can result in imbalances in the body without considering their individual Prakriti. The proposed work aims to collect and prepares a meaningful dataset for Prakriti assessment, which will provide insights into the best breakfast, lunch, and dinner diets to suggest. The MLPClassifier, a neural network-based machine learning technique, will be used for Prakriti classification. By integrating knowledge from Ayurveda, machine learning, and human food interaction, the work seeks to raise awareness of the Ayurvedic diet and classify an individual's Prakriti based on their physiological and psychological characteristics.

Keywords—Ayurveda, MLPClassifier, Machine Learning, Ayurvedic dietary System

I. INTRODUCTION

Ayurveda is one of the world's oldest medical sciences, originating more than five thousand years ago on the Indian subcontinent. It is known as the "Science of Life" or the "Mother of Healing" and encompasses various therapies, including diet, yoga, and herbal preparations, to restore harmony and balance within the body. Ayurveda's principles are based on the concept of Tridoshas - Vata, Pitta, and Kapha - which are dynamic forces with distinct characteristics that shape all things in the universe. These forces are a combination of Panchamahabhutas- Prithvi, Jal, Agni, Vayu, and Akash in different permutations and combinations. In humans, the Doshas control all mental, emotional, and physical functions and responses, determine the state of the soul, and produce natural urges and individual preferences in food. They govern the maintenance and destruction of bodily tissue and the elimination of waste products. One of Ayurveda's primary aims is to maintain the health of healthy individuals, with diet (Ahara) being the most significant of the three pillars of health, responsible for the human body's growth and development. In today's era, to increase one's quality of life and reduce health care expenses, it is essential to be aware of one's Prakriti and the diet that best suits their body constitution.

A. Prakriti

Prakriti is a distinct concept in Ayurveda that defines an individual's fundamental constitution. The term "pra" means original, and "kriti" means creation in Sanskrit. Prakriti

influences both physiological and psychological tendencies, including features such as skin texture, hair color, eye color, finger length, palm shape, body frame, and digestion strength, as well as psychological traits like introversion, extroversion, calmness, excitability, intensity, and laid-back nature. Prakriti is qualitative and quantitative and usually remains unchanged throughout a person's life from birth to death. It plays a significant role in maintaining one's health, personal life, family life, and professional life.

B. Types of Prakriti

Understanding an individual's distinctive constitution enables us to determine the appropriate food, drinks, job types, and exercises for maintaining their health. When the constitution is known, herbs, diets, and other regimens, including yogic postures, can be advised correctly for both disease treatment and lifespan promotion. Knowledge of one's Prakriti allows a person to prevent various disorders from developing and promote their health. Prakriti plays a vital role in the onset, occurrence, management, and treatment of a disease. Ayurveda recommends following these guidelines to prevent various disorders and promote health.

C. Reason to know the Prakriti

People are classified into seven composition kinds in the Ayurvedic medical system based on prakriti. These are classified as pure types (VATT, PITT, KAPH), mixed kinds (VATT-PITT, VATT-KAPH, PITT-KAPH), or equal types (VATT-PITT-KAPH). Each individual has a unique balance of all three energies or combination of two or more.

1. Ekadoshaja : Single dosha predominant (Vata - Water + Air, Pitta - Fire + Water or Kapha - Earth + Water)
2. Dwandwaja : Dual dosha predominant (VATT - PITT, PITT - KAPH, KAPH - VATT)
3. Tridoshaja/ Sannipataja : Tridosha predominant (VATT - PITT - KAPH)

Only a few people are Ekadoshaja Prakriti, while the vast majority are Dwandwaja or Dwidoshaja Prakriti. However, for diagnostic and physiological purposes, Vata, Pitta, and Kapha pradhana Prakriti are considered.

D. Ways to know Individual's Prakriti

Some of the Physical and Psychological characteristics exhibited by each Prakriti are enlisted in the figure given below.

S.NO	CHARACTERISTICS	VATA	PITTA	KAPHA
1	Body Frame	Thin and Lean	Medium	Well Built
2	Weight	Low, Difficult to Put on Weight	Medium, Can Easily Lose or Gain Weight	Overweight, Difficult to Lose Weight
3	Skin Color and Complexion	Dark, Blackish	Pink to Red	Glowing, White
4	Skin Characteristics	Dry, Rough	Delicate, irritable skin prone to rashes and pimples	Slightly oily, Smooth, thick skin
5	Sweat	scanty even in heat	sweat even in cold weather	sweat is moderate and consistent
6	Head Hair	Dry, Very Curly and with Spits End	Thin, Quite Straight and early baldness	Greasy, slightly wavy and thick
7	Nails	hard, brittle nails that are rough and may differ in size.	soft, strong, somewhat rubbery and well formed	strong, large and symmetrical
8	Eyeball	Unsteady, Fast Moving	Moving Slowly	Calm and Steady
9	Size and Teeth Color	Crooked or Uneven teeth, grayish in color	Even teeth of medium size, Yellow, Orange or Red	Large, even, gleaming teeth, Shinning White
10	Eating Habit	Eats Quickly Without Chewing Properly	Eats at a Moderate Speed	Chews Food Properly
11	Hunger	Irregular, Any Time	Sudden Hunger Pangs, Sharp Hunger	Can Skip any Meal Easily
12	Bowel Movements	Dry, Hard, Blackish, Scanty Stools	Soft, Yellowish, Loose Stools	Heavy, Thick, Stick Stools
13	Intolerance to Weather Conditions	Aversion to Cold	Aversion to Heat	Aversion to Moist, Rainy and Cool Weather
14	Mood	Changes quickly have frequent mood swings	Changes Slowly	Stable Constant
15	Body Energy	Becomes Low in Evening, Fatigues After Less Work	Moderate, Gets Tired After Medium Work	Excellent Energy Throughout day not easily Fatigued
16	Pulse	Thin, Shallow and Fast with a Broken or Variable rhythm	Full, Regular, and Strong, with medium speed and rhythm	Strong, Full, Slow and rhythm
17	Sleep	Interrupted, Less	Moderate	Sleep heavily, Lazy
18	Dreams	Dream a lot, often violent and forget their dreams easily	Dreams are passionate and remember what they dream	Dreams are cool, peaceful and do not bother to remember such dreams
19	Communication Skills	Speak quickly, often with rising pitch at the end of a phase	Concise and one-pointed in what they say	Speak slowly and cautiously, without volunteering much.
20	Quality of Voice	Rough with broken words	Commanding	Soft and Deep
21	Social Relations	Make Less Friends, Prefers Solitude	Good No. of Friends	Love to Socialize, Relationships are Longer Lasting
22	Mental Activity	Quick, Restless	Smart Intellect, Aggressive	Calm, Stable
23	Memory	Short Term, Bad	Good Memory	Long Term, Best
24	Grasping Power	Grasps quickly but not completely and forgets quickly.	Grasps quickly but completely and have good memory	Grasps late and retains for longer time
25	Joints	Weak, Noise on Movements	Healthy with Optimal Strength	Heavy Weight Bearing
26	Walking Pace	Quick, Fast with Long Steps	Average Steady	Slow with Short steps
27	Nature	Timid, Jealous	Egotic, Fearless	Forgiving, Greatful, Not Greedy
28	Wealth	Spends without thinking much	Saves but spends on valuable things	Prefers more savings
29	Pace of Performing Work	Fast, Always in Hurry	Medium, Energetic	Slow, Steady
30	Body Temperature	Less than Normal, Hand and Feet are cold	More than Normal, Face and Forehead Hot	Normal, Hands and Feet Slightly Cold

Fig.1. Characteristics of Tri-dosha

II. OBJECTIVE OF THE PROJECT

The goal of this study is to take into account various important aspects of the user's body constituents and ensure that these factors are taken into account as the system works on a solution to build and recommend a healthy and nutritious diet for the users, based on their body state. In this fast-developing competitive world, people in today's society lead modern lives with little time for self-care. It is not a simple issue, but modern living can cause serious health problems in humans. Despite the fact that few people are aware of and eager to learn about diet and nutrition, they blindly follow what they see in newspapers, television, and other forms of media. However, due to the variety of Prakriti, not all foods are suitable for everyone. As a result, such advertisements are broad and marketing-oriented, according to Ayurveda. Ayurveda prescribes various foods and lifestyles based on one's Prakriti and suggests that these guidelines be followed to prevent various disorders and promote health. Therefore, a good nutritious healthy diet and a moderate amount of physical activity can help in maintaining a healthy lifestyle.

III. SCOPE OF THE PROJECT

Fast-food consumption is alarmingly high, resulting in the consumption of unhealthy foods. This causes a variety of health problems such as obesity, diabetes, an increase in blood pressure, and so on. As a result, it has become critical for people to consume a well-balanced, nutritionally sound diet. However, in this fast-paced generation, not everyone has the time or money to spend on a personal dietitian and nutritionist who will look after and care for their health by advising them on a healthy diet plan based on their personal

information. The benefits of knowing Prakriti helps the individual in the following ways:

- A personal analysis of Prakriti helps you know about your body and its requirements.
- Knowing your Prakriti can help you maintain optimal health.
- It will help to maintain a good and balanced personal, family, and professional life.
- Helps to plan a lifestyle according to the requirements of the body.
- Prakriti analysis will help plan a balanced diet.
- This can help to know the likely occurrence of qualitative and quantitative imbalance in the body.

This proposed work is concerned with individuals who have unhealthy eating habits and attempts to provide them with a satisfactory solution for a healthy life. The overall outcome of the project is to develop a web application for people who are consulted about their diet and living healthy life.

IV. LITERATURE SURVEY

A. *Ayurveda and medicalisation today: The loss of important knowledge and practice in health, M. M.Mathpati, S. Albert, J. D. H. Porter, Jan 2020*

This paper investigates how the medicalization of Ayurveda affects its knowledge, education, and practice, as well as the medicalization of the profession. It investigates the impact and contribution of processes such as standardization, specialization, biomedical research, and pharmaceuticals to Ayurvedic education, knowledge, practices, and policies. To maintain health and well-being, Ayurvedic knowledge and practices must be applied at the individual, community, and health levels, rather than just in the health care system.

B. *Computerized pragmatic assessment of Prakriti Dosha using tongue images- Pilot Study, Joshi Manisha S, Umadevi V and Akshitha Raj B N, 2020*

To design an intelligent system to identify Prakriti of a person based on tongue image analysis and machine learning algorithms. Tongue images were captured using webcam and processing was done using Raspberry Pi development board. The algorithms were developed using OpenCV python libraries. Thirteen geometry features, two non-geometry features, and two texture attributes were extracted from each tongue image. These features were used to identify prakriti Vata, Pitta and Kapha. Performance of three classifiers namely, KNN, Neural network and Decisiontree was verified for the precision in identifying class of the test image.

V. METHODOLOGY

A. *One-Hot Encoding*

One-Hot Encoder is used to convert categorical data into numerical data. The dataset contains categorical features with multiple categories. One-Hot Encoder converts each category of the categorical features into a binary column.

B. MLP Classifier

In the proposed work, the MLPClassifier has been chosen due to its ability to effectively learn complex non-linear relationships between input and output variables. The MLPClassifier can handle categorical data by encoding it into a numerical format, such as one-hot encoding. This allows the MLPClassifier to learn complex patterns in the data and accurately classify categorical variables.

C. Streamlit

The application is developed using the Streamlit library and uses a trained model to predict the individual's body constitution based on their responses to a set of questions related to their physical attributes, eating habits, and bodily functions. The application provides a personalized diet recommendation based on the predicted body constitution.

D. System Architecture

The system designed is a Prakriti Diet Recommender, based on Ayurvedic principles. It takes into account the user's body constitution or "prakriti" and recommends a personalized diet accordingly.

- The trained machine learning model is loaded using pickle and consists of an encoder and a classifier. The encoder is used to convert the user's input data into numerical data, which is then fed into the classifier to predict the user's body constitution.
- Based on the predicted body constitution, the system recommends a diet that is appropriate for the user. The recommendations are presented using images and text, which are displayed using Streamlit, a web application framework for Python..

VI. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

Classification of prakriti is performed based on the individual's body constituents. The entire section deals with the experimental setup of the proposed machine learning algorithm.

A. Data Collection

The study gathered data on physical and psychological characteristics through questionnaires referencing Ayurvedic books, specifically Dr. Robert E. Svoboda's "Prakriti Your Ayurvedic Constitution," from individuals aged 18-35 who were students or employees, dividing them equally among dosha classes for improved model performance.

B. Data Pre-processing

The data underwent preprocessing to convert categorical variables to numerical data using OneHotEncoder from the sci-kit-learn library. The data was also split into training and testing sets using the train and test split function from sci-kit-learn.

C. Model Training

After preprocessing, an MLPClassifier from scikit-learn was employed to train a neural network. The model was trained using the training data obtained in Step 2. MLPClassifier is a feedforward neural network that is trained using backpropagation. The model is trained on the entire training set and then tested on the training and testing sets to calculate the accuracy.

D. Model evaluation

The model's accuracy is evaluated using both training and testing data and cross-validation to ensure it generalizes well to new data, generating a classification report with precision, recall, and F1 scores for each class in the testing set. This helps estimate the model's performance on unseen data.

E. Model Prediction

Finally, the trained model was utilized to predict an individual's body type based on various attributes. This information was then used to provide diet recommendations based on the Ayurvedic tradition. Using Streamlit a user interface is created that allows the user to select a meal (breakfast, lunch, or dinner) and enter their personal information such as body frame, weight, skin color, etc. The user interface uses the option menu function from the streamlit option menu library to create a dropdown menu for meal selection.

VII. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The proposed algorithm applied on Ayurveda constitution data predicts an individual's prakriti using an ANN model. The model is trained with 80% of the data and tested with 20%. The confusion matrix shows that the model correctly identifies all instances of each class, indicating there are no false positives or negatives and the model performs well with the dataset for recommending the best diet.

A. Design of Web Application

The user interface uses the option menu function from the streamlit option menu library to create a dropdown menu for meal selection. The user interface also displays a title, subtitle, and several dropdown menus for entering personal information.

Firstly, the user selects the specific type of meal.

Then the user has to give the input to predict the prakriti of an individual.

Once the user enters their information and clicks the "Prediction results" button, it predicts the body state and displays the corresponding diet recommendations and image.

VIII. CONCLUSION

The proposed algorithm applied on Ayurveda constitution data predicts an individual's prakriti using an ANN model. The model is trained with 80% of the data and tested with 20%. The confusion matrix shows that the model correctly identifies all instances of each class, indicating there are no false positives or negatives and the model performs well with the dataset for recommending the best diet.

IX. LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE WORKS

MLP can take longer to train, especially with large and complex data, due to backpropagation updating all network weights. The proposed work used deep learning techniques, opening up new areas of investigation. With doctor approval, the model can classify patients' body constituents for optimal food consumption, enhancing their health.

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